

Assessment of Medical Student Perceptions of Novel Teaching and Learning through Movie Screen Shots

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Abstract:

Background of the Study: Medical and educational methodologies and strategies have advanced worldwide in recent decades. The contemporary method places greater emphasis on the student, emphasizing the development of skills. The undergraduate course curriculum for the National Medical Commission (NMC) has been recently updated to follow a competency-based approach, known as competency-based medical education (CBME), instead of the old outcome-based curriculum. Embracing innovative teaching-learning and educational methodologies is crucial for achieving the goal of competency-based medical education (CBME).

Objective: To investigate the perspectives of students on an innovative pedagogical approach in medical education.

Materials & Method: The research study was conducted on final MBBS phase - 1 student studying ophthalmology at Government Medical College in Nellore, India. The study was conducted 109 final years Phase – 1 MBBS Students. An innovative teaching-learning technique was used. A topic in ophthalmology, "glaucoma," was taught using a teaching method that incorporated online movie screenshots, with the help of an analogy from a Telugu movie episode (Vinodam, 1996), the characters were compared to Glaucoma, an ocular condition, Glaucoma Patient and an Ophthalmologist, the scene was explained with the help of a movie screenshot. After the activity, students' feedback was obtained using a self-designed; pilot tested and validated eight item closed-ended questionnaires with options based on a 5-point Likert scale.

Results; 60 out of 109 students responded to the questionnaire about movie screenshot-based teaching methods. 41(68.3%) students agreed that they were more satisfied. 13(21.67%) students disagreed that they were more satisfied. 6(10 %) remained neutral. 41(68.3%) students agreed that they felt motivated to learn. 10(16.67%) students disagreed that they felt motivated to learn. 9(15%) remained neutral. 41(68.3%) students agreed that they prefer the movie screenshot method. 17(28.33%) students disagreed that they prefer the movie screenshot method. 2(3.33%) remained neutral. 36(60%) students agreed that their learning experience was enriching. 10(16.67%) students disagreed that their learning experience was enriching. 14(23.33 %) remained neutral.

Conclusion: Applying a movie-based scenario in films has demonstrated its efficacy and entertainment value in increasing students' understanding of Facilitating learning tough topics like "Glaucoma" in Ophthalmology.

Keywords: Novel teaching, medical Education, cinema education.

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Introduction

New ideas and methods for medical education have been encouraged to arise as a result of the advancement of the medical sciences. [1]. Methods that are commonly adopted include student-centered philosophies that aim to promote student engagement in learning, allowing students to pursue their personal interests through the increased prominence of elective courses, and anticipating content that is clinically oriented. Medical schools are increasingly incorporating digital resources,

simulation training, early emphasis on teamwork, and the cultivation of soft skills into their curricula. Major changes to undergraduate medical education have occurred within the last several decades. [2], the field of education is one area where information and communication technologies are applied [3]. The use of electronic systems, particularly Internet technology, to provide a variety of options for enhancing performance and understanding is known as e-learning. Additionally, a growing number of

students are using mobile devices as instruments for information search because access to them has been made easier by a number of inexpensive items. [4,5]. Medical students are familiar with these advancements. Furthermore, they will utilize state-of-the-art instruments for the purposes of diagnosing, treating, and making decisions in their future professional endeavors.

Students nowadays exhibit a stronger inclination towards technology, which is attributed to their diverse learning methods. [6,7] Their utilization of technology entails novel methods of acquiring knowledge. Furthermore, conventional instructional techniques, such as in-person lectures (FLs), no longer suffice to fulfill the requirements of undergraduate students on their own [8,9]. IT has the ability to change the way medical education is done, and students are the ones who can use it most quickly [10].

Quick access to information gives teachers a great chance to come up with new ways to teach and meet the needs of the current program. Students who can learn at their own pace can use recorded lessons (RLs) and movie screen shots that are made public online through a local area network or the Internet. Because screen shots are flexible, students can learn at their own pace and when they have time. They can also go over tough ideas again and make more notes. [11,12].

Novel Interactive pedagogical methods in comparative medical education by using movie screenshots to facilitate associative learning in medical students could be effective but are rarely practiced.

Moreover, there has been a paucity of studies exploring the prospects of associative learning based on using movie screenshots metaphorically conveying generic and subliminal patterns of similarity and dissimilarity for better comparison in medical education. This educational study is undertaken to plug these research gaps.

Methods

Study design: This study was mixed methods approach- combining quantitative and qualitative data through structured and open- ended questions. We analyzed qualitative data and Quantitative data in the form of Structured Questionnaire (duly validated) containing 10 questions with statements regarding the students' perceptions about the use of Movie Screenshots as metaphoric equivalents were administered at the end of the session. Analysis of open-ended questions identified three major themes. These were: (1) movie screenshot-based teaching: enjoyable and useful; (2) widening of perspective: different ways of thinking; (3) increased connectivity: long term memory; these themes evidenced professional growth on the part of students attending class.

Participants: The research study was conducted on final MBBS phase - I students studying ophthalmology at ACSR Government Medical College in Nellore, India. 109 students from Final MBBS Phase I were taught about an Ophthalmology topic i.e., "Glaucoma" with an online movie screenshot-based teaching method. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of ACSR Govt medical college Ethics Committee with approval number ECR/961/Inst/AP/2017/RR-20/72-01/14-12-2020. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, after explanation of the study's objectives. All participants were assured of the confidentiality of the information to be collected and that they were free to decline to participate in the study. Data acquisition followed the self-administered questionnaire without the intervention of the specific person and it did not contain any identifying data of the participants to ensure confidentiality. Only filled questionnaires were included for the data analysis.

Figure 1:

Data Collection: A topic in ophthalmology, "glaucoma," was taught using a teaching method that incorporated online movie screenshots, with the help of an analogy from a telugu movie episode (Vinodam,1996), the characters were compared to Glaucoma, an ocular condition, Glaucoma Patient and Ophthalmologist, the scene was explained with the help of a movie screenshot.

A smart thief who gets trained in a college for thieves, in a movie deceives and tries to steal things on installment basis in a house, in the presence of its owner who was blind folded after a trauma, his

wife, his friend and a known police officer, without being recognised as a thief by giving them the impression that he is a relative of the owner, friend or the police officer to each other. After the activity, students' feedback was obtained using a ten item open-ended questionnaire. Each question had five choices (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, or strongly disagree). Feedback data was collected from the Google form, which was emailed to all the student participants. The ten-item feedback form was self-designed, pilot tested and checked for face validity, content validity, and reliability.

Movie screenshot used in the novel teaching method

Figure 2:

Results

60 out of 109 students responded to the questionnaire about movie screenshot-based teaching methods. 49(81.6%) students disagreed that they get distracted from the topic with the use

of movie screenshots. 7(11.6%) students agreed that they get distracted. 4(6.67%) remained neutral. 48(80%) students disagreed that they feel bored.

9(15%) students agreed that they feel bored. 3(5%) remained neutral.

Table 1:

Qualitative data:	
Students' Perception of open-ended questions are:	
Advantages	Disadvantages
1. Easily remembered and understood.	1. If remember something in that movie is good, I will be in that visual world of that movie leaving the class
2. Makes me active to listen to topics	2. I didn't understand the language
3. Able to understand much more than usual lectures.	3. If had not seen the movie, I cannot understand the context
4. Easy interlink of points and able to remember for long time	
5. Sudden seeing of picture tries to remember that movie and co relate to current topic, which activates brain.	

Discussion

It is well known that many countries around the world use films to teach medical students about professional problems. To make things clearer, let's put the new ways of teaching, learning, and assessing into Bloom's taxonomy of learning areas and compare them to the out-dated tools.

Video snippets from the television show 'The Doctor' were utilised in the United States to educate residents on psychological topics, including the communication of negative information, the effects of terminal disease, and the challenges of cultural diversity in the field of medicine. Following the presentation of movie snippets and screen shots, the project incorporated discussion questions and role plays. [13].

The utilization of standardized essays in qualitative research is well acknowledged. We opted to scrutinize the substance of essays, since we believed this approach would provide a more thoughtful perspective compared to the conventional methods of using questionnaires or interviews. Students are accustomed to creating reflective pieces as a component of their coursework. After having sufficient time to contemplate the strengths and weaknesses of their clinical education, the replies they provide may offer certain benefits compared to data collected in direct, in-person settings.

This study demonstrates that Movie Screen shots produce the same knowledge gain as traditional face-to-face lectures, making them suitable for clinical courses. Screen Shots are effective at increasing knowledge in medical students. Similar findings were observed in other researches.

In Brazil, the Academic Department of the Brazilian Society of Family Medicine did an educational project called "Literature and Movies for Medical Students", in which students from various medical schools in Sao Paulo State participated in a group discussion after they had read books or watched selected films [15].

Some studies recommend watching the entire movie as part of the learning process [16,17], while others support using film clips to generate group discussion, points of view, and trigger emotions and thoughts from the viewer's [14,18]. We found that although watching the entire movie was time-consuming, it helped to provide the background of each character and make we, the preclinical students, understand the many controversial issues in the movie more easily Blasco et al suggested that using the literature and films before an open discussion among students, and facilitating faculty educators to highlight emerging topics, has proven to be a useful and enjoyable way of teaching, which successfully reflects in the personal and professional attitudes and values of medical students [15]. In

our project, the group discussion was led by medical students, not educators, in order to stimulate one another to express views more openly. However, students must be careful not to be misled during the discussion by exaggerated content in the movie, the so-called "halo" or "Rashomon" effect Ber and Alroy [19].

The use of videos& screen shots has been shown as an effective and innovative method of teaching, as reported in many recent articles in the medical literature (Alexander 2002). Movies have many advantages, in that students can engage in and gain acceptance from them. They can make abstract and dry content become alive and understandable and promote various kinds of learning methods [20]. Also, movies present a direct teaching scenario, in which particular scenes indicate important issues. Another benefit in using movies to teach professionalism is that emotions are depicted in accessible ways and they are easy to identify [18].

Most of the studies on the use of movies in medical education applied qualitative approach to data analysis. Our study has some similarities with the recent study by Alis and Nazan (2014). Both studies conducted an analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data derived from questionnaires, which were distributed after the students had watched the movies followed by a facilitator-moderated discussion. Regarding the study results, Alis and Nazan (2014) [21] showed that 88% of films used by them in medical education were rated as good by the students, and 54% of their respondents felt that terminally ill patients were fully portrayed in a very realistic way in the movies, which is consistent with our findings. Similar to our findings, most of the students (81.9%) in their study were personally satisfied after watching screen shots. Adlina Suleiman showed that the medical students felt that movies enhanced their learning related to personal and professional development and could motivate the applicability of medical education concepts.

Our study also showed that movie screenshot-based teaching may help in associative and hence accumulative learning. Our students also acknowledged that this project had helped them understand the impact of illness on patients and their families. In addition, it also prepared them to face inevitable situations, which they would have to encounter in clinical years, by watching scenarios from the movies and discussing how to deal with them, or whether they agreed with each character's decision.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the "Cinema education Project" has proven to be another effective and entertaining method of facilitating learning tough topics like "Glaucoma" in Ophthalmology.

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